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**Features of organization the distance learning
in the training of military specialists**

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Abstract. *The military sphere is one of the most important components of social existence, just as military education is an essential part of the overall educational system. In times of war, the issue of organizing distance learning in military educational institutions becomes especially relevant. **The purpose of article** is to analyze the peculiarities of organizing distance learning in military higher education institutions and to develop recommendations for applying key principles of andragogy in the training of military specialists. Several scientific methods were used in the research process: theoretical analysis of scientific literature on pedagogy and andragogy, and experimental method. **The results of the study** emphasize that military personnel, as individuals undergoing military education, are adults with considerable experience; however, the teaching of certain subjects, as well as the development of critical thinking and leadership skills in this group, requires a different approach – namely, a higher level of individualized instruction. One of the ways to solve this problem is the application of distance learning. In military education – particularly in*

the context of distance learning for students and cadets of higher military institutions – andragogy plays a significant role, introducing instructors to a broad range of issues related to adult education.

Conclusions. *The results of the study indicate differences in the fundamental principles of pedagogical and andragogical models of education. It has been noted that distance learning in the military sphere – especially under wartime conditions – is effective and, at times, the only viable means of obtaining quality education. Examples of the use of distance learning technologies for training military specialists are presented, and key issues in implementing distance learning in the military sphere are identified. It is proposed that, for obtaining an operational-strategic level of military education, a promising model of distance learning could be a consortium of higher military educational institutions. The relevance of organizing distance learning based on andragogical principles has been substantiated. The advantages of applying andragogical approaches in the training of future military specialists are outlined. The specific features of applying andragogical principles in distance learning for students and cadets of higher military educational institutions have been identified. It has been noted that the use of andragogical principles contributes to the development of effective educational programs that meet the needs of military specialists. The advisability of including these principles in the professional development system for instructors has been emphasized.*

Keywords: *military education, military personnel, distance learning, andragogy, independent work, cognitive activity.*

**Особливості організації дистанційного навчання
при підготовці військових фахівців**

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***Анотація.** Військова сфера є ключовим елементом суспільного існування, як і військова освіта є необхідним складником загальної освітньої системи. В умовах війни набуває актуальності питання організації дистанційного навчання у військових навчальних закладах. Метою статті є аналіз особливостей організації дистанційного навчання у військових вишах та розробка рекомендацій щодо застосування ключових принципів андрагогіки у процесі підготовки військових фахівців. У процесі дослідження було використано декілька наукових методів: теоретичний аналіз наукової літератури з педагогіки та андрагогіки, та експериментальний метод. Результати дослідження акцентуються на тому, що військовослужбовці, як ті, що здобувають військову освіту, є дорослими та, здебільшого, досвідченими особами, це вимагає підвищення рівня індивідуалізованого навчання, що, в свою чергу, сприяє розвитку критичного мислення та лідерських якостей тих, хто навчається. Одним зі шляхів вирішення вказаної проблеми є застосування дистанційного навчання. У військовій освіті, зокрема, при дистанційному навчанні слухачів та курсантів вищих військових навчальних закладів, важливе місце посідає андрагогіка, яка вводить викладачів у широке коло проблем освіти дорослих.*

***Висновки.** Результати проведеного дослідження свідчать про відмінності в основних положеннях педагогічної та андрагогічної моделей здобуття освіти. Зазначено, що дистанційне навчання у військовій сфері, особливо в умовах війни, є ефективним, а інколи й єдиним з можливих шляхів*

отримання якісної освіти. Наведено приклади використання технологій дистанційного навчання військових фахівців та визначено проблемні питання при впровадженні дистанційного навчання у військовій сфері. Наголошено, що при здобутті оперативно-стратегічного рівня військової освіти перспективною моделлю дистанційного навчання може вважатися консорціум військових закладів вищої освіти. Доведено актуальність питань організації дистанційного навчання на засадах андрагогіки. Розкрито переваги використання андрагогічних принципів у процесі навчання майбутніх військових фахівців. Визначено особливості застосування андрагогічних принципів у дистанційному навчанні слухачів та курсантів військових закладів вищої освіти. Відмічено, що використання андрагогічних принципів сприяє створенню ефективних навчальних програм, що відповідають потребам військових фахівців. Вказано на доцільність викладання даних принципів в системі підвищення кваліфікації викладачів.

Ключові слова: *військовослужбовці, військова освіта, дистанційне навчання, андрагогіка, самостійна робота, пізнавальна діяльність.*

Problem statement. The rapid advancement of science and technology leads to the relatively quick obsolescence of professional knowledge, necessitating its continuous renewal and deepening without interrupting service or professional activity. At present, in our country, special attention is being focused on military education, there is research into effective methods and forms of training, introduction of new approaches to military education, use of existing and search for new ways of staffing the Armed Forces of Ukraine with officer personnel. This requires a comprehensive study of modern educational approaches, selection, improvement and adaptation of modern educational technologies for use in military educational institutions. Individuals who receive a military education are mature and experienced in life. The science of the theory and methodology of organising adult learning is called

andragogy [1].

After the end of the Second World War, adult education revealed significant differences in educational processes organized according to pedagogical and andragogical models, which led to the emergence of andragogy as a distinct field of study [2]. The knowledge and skills acquired in youth remain important and useful throughout life; however, it is essential and practical to prepare individuals for interaction with new phenomena, technologies, conditions, and events. Under such conditions, the knowledge and practical skills acquired up to a certain point in time become irrelevant. Younger and adult learners have significantly different motivation to learn. Younger students perceive education as the acquisition of subject-specific knowledge, some of which may be useful to them in the future.

Thus, education ceases to be the transmission of established knowledge and becomes a process of continuous knowledge renewal throughout life. In other words, it loses its initial one-time character and takes on the features of a sequential, systematic, and ongoing process, as the modern labor market in civilian life and operational-combat activities in the military sphere demand that specialists possess not only deep theoretical knowledge but also the ability to independently acquire and apply it in non-standard, constantly changing conditions [3].

The leading role in adult education belongs to the learners themselves – that is, they become subjects approaching the status of those who teach. Therefore, one of the important features of this process is the learner's participation in choosing the educational direction, selecting and structuring the content and pace of learning, as well as its forms and technologies. Thus, military education – especially distance learning – may be viewed as a collaborative, non-authoritarian interaction, in which the instructor primarily serves as the more experienced participant.

Analysis of significant research and publications. The development of the key principles of andragogy and their practical implementation in the educational process is investigated in [1; 4–6]. At the same time, [7] pays considerable attention to the

application of the andragogical model in higher education institutions of European Union.

The presented principles differ significantly from traditional pedagogical approaches [8], which is undoubtedly due to the specific perception of the educational process by an adult and a much higher level of his/her motivation for learning [9]. Given the complex realities of today, when obtaining education without interrupting professional duties, the organization of effective independent work by learners becomes a priority – its specifics are discussed in [10; 11]. In this regard, both instructors and students should focus their efforts on improving distance education technologies [3; 12–14]. Works [13–18] analyzed problems, definitions and methods of distance learning in general, without taking into account the specifics for different spheres, in particular military. In study [19], approaches to distance learning in different countries are compared, and prospects for Ukrainian civilian universities are outlined. With regard to the direct organization of distance learning, study [20] proposes ways of implementing it within the domestic educational landscape, whereas approaches to organizing distance education in the military sphere have not yet been fully formulated [21]. In the conditions of war, but in safer regions, the mixed form of education, providing a combination of distance and face-to-face forms of organization of the educational process, is relevant [15; 17]. Undoubtedly, the implementation of distance learning requires the adoption of cutting-edge innovative tools and technologies – both for delivering knowledge and for assessing its assimilation – namely, the development and use of electronic learning courses and tests, as discussed in [19–22].

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Despite significant developments, modern subject teaching in military educational institutions faces still unresolved problems.

In today's warfare environment, distance learning is sometimes the only means of training and continually maintaining a high level of military expertise. At the same

time, the application of distance learning in the military sphere brings certain challenges. These challenges are related to the specific nature of service for those undergoing training, the need for practical exercises both at training grounds and in simulation complexes equipped with specialized equipment, as well as limited access to information and certain types of weaponry and military hardware. Undoubtedly, a constraining factor in such training is the need to ensure reliable cybersecurity. It is worth noting that cadets and students of higher military educational institutions are adult learners who have a strong psychological need for autonomy; therefore, instructors must be familiar with and skillfully apply the principles of andragogy. Unlike younger students, whose achievements are evaluated by the teacher, adult learning can often be based on their successes and failures in life and professional life. The experiences of adult learners become a rich source of useful information for themselves and others. The value of information gained from one's own experience is much higher than information gained passively. The education of younger schoolchildren should be organized according to clearly standardized programs and schedules, with corresponding expected outcomes. Adults, on the other hand, become ready to learn when they feel the need to improve themselves and acquire new knowledge that will help them to meet the challenges of professional or service activities and to deal more effectively with the problems of everyday life. Thus, there is a need to develop guidelines for educating adult military professionals who view education as a means of enhancing their competence in order to realize their full professional and personal potential. They require knowledge and practical skills that can be applied 'here and now' and that offer the prospect of further expansion, deepening, and refinement.

Formulation of article objectives. Based on the above, the aim of the article is to analyze the specifics of organizing distance learning in military educational institutions and to develop recommendations for applying key principles of andragogy in the training of military professionals.

Statement of the main research material. Distance learning is deservedly called the educational system of the XXI century. Today, the learning process and the performance of duties are perceived as virtually one and the same thing. Taking into account the current dynamics of science and technology, professional knowledge is losing relevance at a fairly high rate, which implies the need for continuous, and accordingly – preferably, distance learning. Today, the number of students engaged in distance learning worldwide exceeds those attending full-time programs at higher education institutions. For individuals accustomed to independent work, capable of analyzing educational material, and driven by clear goals with persistence, distance education is built upon a key element of the learning process – independent study [11] – which offers real opportunities for acquiring the competencies necessary for their future profession.

Distance learning in the form of so-called distance learning dates back to the beginning of the last century. Despite the high prevalence of distance learning, its quality has traditionally been assessed lower than that of full-time education. Several factors were involved, including inadequate communication between instructors and students, as well as a lack of oversight during the learning process between initial and final sessions. In other words, the issue ultimately lay in the educational technology itself. The capabilities of modern computer technologies enable the rapid and continuous dissemination of knowledge, and access to educational and scientific information can sometimes be even more effective than through traditional instructional methods.

An indicative trend in modern distance education is the merging of university organizational structures. Thus, a new type of organizational structure of distance university education has recently begun to develop – a consortium of universities. That is, distance education services are provided by a special organization that unites and coordinates the activities of several universities. The university consortium offers a wide range of courses developed by various universities, ranging from preparatory

courses for prospective students to programs leading to academic degrees. This is a promising model for use in the operational-strategic level education of officers, where it is necessary to learn how to plan operations involving various branches or types of armed forces. It is evident that, in this case, the consortium must include military educational institutions and ensure an appropriate level of information security.

At the end of the last century, many countries established national open universities. While they adopted a significant number of organizational principles from distance education, open education as a whole introduced many innovations into the educational system. The principle of openness of education provides for the freedom of enrolment of students and drawing up an individual curriculum, as well as freedom of place, time and pace of study. Open learning is based on a rich and well-structured educational environment in which the learner navigates independently and strives to achieve their self-defined educational goals.

The implementation of the principle of openness has led to significant organizational changes, which became practically feasible due to the introduction of new technologies for storing, processing, and transmitting information. For example, there is a new model of distance education based on teleconferencing, which can take place both between instructor and students and between students themselves. The model of online lectures and teleconferences leads to radical changes in the organization of modern education. This is manifested in the fact that a new organizational form of modern education – virtual universities – has started to develop on the basis of this model. This model fully realizes the potential for redesigning the education system, allowing groups of students and individual students to 'meet' teachers and each other at any distance from each other. These modern communication tools are complemented by computer-based educational programs. The emergence of such a model of distance education results in the learning process taking place not only remotely, but also independently of any specific educational institution.

In the field of military education, physical absence from the educational

institution is undoubtedly a significant advantage for service members pursuing education without interrupting their official duties. However, it should be noted that distance learning can give a significant result in the theoretical training of a military specialist or preliminary preparation for practical exercises, while the practical component of training can be realized only when the instructor supervises the cadets and trainees face-to-face. It is also quite evident that, in higher military educational institutions, only academic subjects – primarily of a humanitarian, socio-economic, and fundamental natural sciences orientation, as well as those included in basic training – may be taught remotely without restricted access.

As for military-professional and professionally specialized training courses, the implementation of distance learning in the field of military education faces significant limitations. These limitations are due not only to access difficulties and cybersecurity concerns, but also to the necessity of mastering modern equipment and weapons systems within a short timeframe – something that is problematic without direct supervision by an instructor or educator.

In training military specialists, it is important to understand that the subject of andragogy is not just the education of an adult, but an education that is significantly related to the fulfilment of professional duties in specific conditions of activity. The following features of applying andragogical principles in distance education of students and cadets of military higher education institutions can be identified:

- students and cadets have a deep psychological need for autonomy, which is undoubtedly supported by distance learning – an approach that, to a greater extent, requires experienced instructors merely to guide their activities;

- knowledge acquired through distance learning is free from the possibility of authoritarian influence by the instructor and is associated by students and cadets with their personal experience in professional and everyday activities – something instructors should place particular emphasis on;

- instructors at higher military educational institutions, in a sense, provide

'educational services'; therefore, they must demonstrate the practical value of the knowledge offered in order to motivate students and cadets to independently acquire, deepen, and refine it.

The above features of adult learning are extremely relevant for teachers, trainees and cadets alike, as they are:

- encourage self-improvement and self-realization;
- allow to deepen and rethink one's own life and professional experience;
- they contribute to the mutual exchange of useful information, enabling students and cadets to direct their efforts and time more effectively, while also allowing instructors to improve the educational process as a whole.

These characteristics should be further developed and provided to instructors as part of a professional development system aimed at equipping them with the necessary qualities to provide andragogical guidance in the distance learning of students and cadets at higher military educational institutions. The most important of these qualities is the ability to apply adaptive forms and methods of teaching, as well as to take into account the individual needs of learners [2; 10].

A key aspect of the direct organization of instruction is the activation of cognitive engagement among participants in distance learning. This is achieved through the use of modern software tools, video materials demonstrating military equipment, and computer simulations, which are recommended for integration into the process of delivering instructional content during lessons. Problem-based learning [8] may also be advisable, as it involves presenting a current problem and formulating relevant questions, rather than passively delivering material. This will contribute to the activation of mental activity of students aimed at solving the task at hand. An unquestionable requirement for distance learning in military higher education institutions – one that is not subject to debate – is a high level of computer literacy and the ability of instructors to use the latest computer and telecommunication technologies in the educational process.

Conclusions. Modern military education is evolving into a sequential, systematic, and continuous process, driven by the necessity for the systematic and independent acquisition of practically essential knowledge and skills. In today's warfare environment, distance learning is often the only viable way to train military professionals. This requires instructors to organize distance learning based on the principles of andragogy, which involve non-authoritarian interaction between educators and learners. A consortium of military higher education institutions may be a promising model of education for operational and strategic officers, which is becoming a reality due to the application of modern computer and telecommunication technologies.

Andragogy plays a key role in modern military education, particularly in the distance learning of students and cadets at higher military educational institutions. As an academic discipline, andragogy immerses teachers in a wide range of sociological, social psychological and cultural issues in adult education. It emphasizes the importance of personalized learning, which is particularly relevant in the military, where the development of critical thinking and leadership skills is essential.

In higher military educational institutions, when organizing distance learning for service members, instructors must take into account the specifics of andragogical principles, which include: a deep psychological need among service members for autonomy and self-improvement; consideration of their existing personal experience in both professional and everyday domains; and the necessity of encouraging them to independently expand and enhance their knowledge. Thus, the use of the andragogical approach facilitates the development of effective educational programs that take into account the professional requirements of military specialists.

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